

IMPROVING STUDENTS' LEARNING ACTIVITY AND TEACHING ENGLISH WITH COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY IN THE CREDIT MODULE SYSTEM

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Abstract. This article provides theoretical and practical recommendations on the development and management of independent educational activities of students in the credit-module education system.

Key words: credit, module, system, pedagogical technology, intellectual capacity, professionalism, skill, method.

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ УЧЕБНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ И ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ С ПОМОЩЬЮ КОМПЬЮТЕРНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СИСТЕМЕ КРЕДИТНЫХ МОДУЛЕЙ

Аннотация. В данной статье даны теоретические и практические рекомендации по развитию и управлению самостоятельной учебной деятельностью студентов в кредитно-модульной системе обучения.

Ключевые слова: кредит, модуль, система, педагогическая технология, интеллектуальный потенциал, профессионализм, умение, метод.

Today, in educational institutions, specialists who meet the requirements of the time are trained not only with deep study of theoretical knowledge, but at the same time a great attention is being paid to educate with great human qualities, who are able to enter into transactions, and become skilled specialists who master their work thoroughly. Especially, this requirement of the current era emphasizes once again that all teachers in educational institutions should be armed with high pedagogical skills and technical skills, capable of creative approach to their pedagogical activities, competent and cultured individuals. The demand of the current period imposes new tasks and several responsibilities on teachers. With the advent of modern technology, the tradition of teaching English has changed significantly. The introduction of digital technologies and modern teaching methods in higher education processes in the "Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 of October 8, 2019, specific tasks are being carried out on wide involvement in scientific activity, introduction of the credit module system,

increasing the share of practical training in specialized subjects aimed at improving practical skills in the curricula.

The credit-module system is a process of educational organization and is an evaluation model based on a set of module technologies of education and a credit measure. Carrying it out as a whole is a complex and versatile process. In the credit-module principle, two main issues are given importance: ensuring independent work of students; assessment of student knowledge based on rating.

The following are recognized as the main tasks of the credit module system:

- organization of educational processes on the basis of modules;
- determining the value of one subject, course (credit);
- evaluation of students' knowledge based on rating points;
- to enable students to create their own study plans individually;
- increasing the share of independent education in the educational process;
- ease of training programs and the ability to change based on the demand for a specialist in the labor market.

The above is not only teaching based on innovative educational technologies, but also independent learning from the student, a new attitude to education, acquiring the necessary and deep theoretical knowledge based on the demand of the labor market. , consists of teaching to form practical skills. In short, this system is aimed at the professional development and maturity of the student. It is aimed at ensuring the education of the scholar throughout his life and at the formation of human capital that can meet the labor market and modern requirements.

Let's briefly touch on the essence of the module and credit concepts here.

A module is a part of the curriculum in which several subjects and courses are studied. It is a set of several subjects (courses) aimed at students' ability to develop certain knowledge and skills, to conduct analytical and logical observation. In this, the teacher organizes the educational process, gives live, video and audio lectures, coordinates and monitors the student's activities. The student learns the subject independently and completes the assigned tasks.

According to foreign experience, the educational process in the credit-module system consists of 2-4 modules per semester. The subjects included in the module are formed from easy to complex, from theoretical-methodical subjects to applied subjects and based on the principle of logical complementarity. In order for a student to become a specialist, it is necessary to have not only information, but also the ability to process it and put it into practice.

Module-based training programs are developed based on a special scheme and include:

- full disclosure of educational goals and tasks;

- the requirements for the student's qualification, which must be acquired after starting and finishing the subject (course);
- summary (syllabus) of each subject included in the module, i.e. topics of lectures, plan of seminar and practical training, tasks intended for independent education assessment;
- a brief description of teaching: methods and means of teaching; consists of methods and forms of knowledge assessment.

In the module-based teaching system, a rating evaluation system is used to assess students' knowledge, skills, and abilities. In it, all the student's educational activities, that is, the knowledge acquired and mastered in the classroom and outside the classroom, are evaluated by giving points.

Nowadays, the importance of learning the English language, which is considered the demand of the times, is becoming much higher in Uzbekistan than before. A number of English language experts are implementing new methods and guides for learning English. This will definitely increase the effectiveness of teaching foreign languages. There are several unique advantages of teaching using technologies. In addition, it greatly increases the efficiency of the teaching system and, in turn, helps the language learner to keep up with the times and move forward. Technology is slowly taking the place of traditional teaching.

Today, a number of new programs and shows that help to teach English are regularly broadcast on television. It should also be noted that today new methods of using modern innovative technologies have been introduced in Uzbekistan to increase the effectiveness of teaching. For example, a student who is being taught a foreign language on the basis of multimedia has the opportunity to develop four skills, i.e. (reading, writing, speaking and listening), to learn both by seeing and listening through interesting materials. In addition, the student can guess the meaning of some words by watching live actions and tries to understand it. Of course, the use of modern technologies such as computers, radios, CDs, and DVDs in any foreign language classes will further develop the educational process and allow the young generation to learn foreign languages faster. lack of knowledge and use of technology leads to some boredom of students. It is for this reason, that is, in order not to extinguish the student's enthusiasm, the use of technologies, various handouts and at least the computer during the lesson ensures that the student's interest increases. After all, educational materials prepared according to the learner's age, interest, ability, mastery of lessons will definitely be effective. Therefore, if we teachers do not choose educational materials based on these requirements, elementary school students will have a difficult time if we do not broadcast video films, songs or texts consisting of words or show them through multimedia, computers, when we show educational materials consisting of very simple texts to middle and high

school students or groups their interest in learning the language gradually fades and they do not master the lessons.

In conclusion, we must say that the role of modern technologies is incomparable in order to enrich our lessons, interest students, enrich their knowledge and enable them to work independently. Being able to use them correctly and appropriately is the main goal of our achievements.

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